

2025 NASA SMD Open Source Science Data Repositories Workshop

Versioning Decision Tool Concept - Virtual
August 25, 2025

- Facilitators:
- Note-Taker: Amelia Pilgrim
- Chat monitor:

ALL DAY MATERIALS CAN BE FOUND HERE

Agenda

- Visit each of five activity stations in small groups (online visit breakout rooms)
- A bell will ring to signal change to another station - mix up and join a new group
- Versioning Decision Tool Concept - Candida Dewes

Pre-Activity

- EXERCISE: Miro board containing a flowchart with guiding questions intended to help the user determine if data is updating with minor or major changes

Speaker/Lightning Talk Notes

- Decision framework was created to help data team make decisions about currently published data set and what can be improved or added to it
 - Have identified series of “triggers” on left side - identified series of common updates that came with common requests
 - Established guiding questions that accompany process
- Sticky: “Do you encounter other TRIGGERS for datasets not represented here?” AKA: Are these triggers relatable? Are there any related questions that make sense in your scenario?
 - “Does archiving location change (on-prem vs cloud)”
 - “Does the data retention policy change?”
 - “How many of the data files will be impacted by the change?”
 - “Recently, we had to discuss if real-time data products that are replaced with definitive products should be archived...”
 - “Related: expense involved in making change”

- “Adding or changing ancillary data (e.g. browse or analysis-ready data) that’s not part of the actual archive”
- “Is there an emerging data standard that needs to be adopted?”
- “Change to metadata requirements?”
- “Moving from many files compressed in a container (e.g. .zip, [tar.gz](#)) to single files”
- Sticky: Did the pathway you landed on make sense for your use case? Why or why not?
 - “yes it makes sense and cause it showcases the way it promotes work ethic and reality” +1
 - yes. I find that the framework is a nice balance between documenting/implementing change and avoiding calling everything a "major" change since that could cause unnecessary thrashing for the users.
 - I liked it, but it made me question about "scientific change" as in substantive vs formal? grammatical?
- Sticky: ““Revision” might translate to “minor version increment” for some and “update without version increment” for others. What does it mean for you?
 - “Revision is adding something in a short amount of time which increases the increment”
 - “For APD, it isn't obvious to me that we have the concept of minor versions for data, only the software that generates it. We tend to use data release nomenclature after reprocessing a large set of data.”
 - “To reduce complexity we could remove "major" and "minor" and consider numerical sequential version increments all the same. Version 1 becomes Version 2 if any change is made to the dataset. I would not expect the dataset doi to change just the version ID”
- Sticky: “Are these questions appropriate for your use case(s)? What others would you add?”
 - “Another question: should the old version be retained indefinitely? Or removed as superseded?” +4
 - I would generalize the questions to a higher level. eg. instead of does author change, does any of the metadata (but not the data) change +2
 - How can we be assured of the novelty about the data and it not being just stolen +2
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 - is storage system changing - only requires a user announcement. not really, there are other things that will need to happen, API updates, registry updates, etc.... +1
 - Will the storage system change trigger the data tool update? +1
 - Does minor versioning not usually end up with a new DOI? LP DAAC has created new DOI for both major and minor version increments.+2

- Notes per change:
 - Major Version Increment
 - Regardless of version increment, all "triggered" updates need to be documented in the version history. +4
 - Downstream systems/data consumption will need to be notified of changes, data change mgmt documented
 - Update without Version Increment
 - "Data being removed **should** trigger a version increment IMO" +4
 - "why would you want to update without (at least a minor) version increment? Any change at all means it's not the same data set any more." +4
 - "yes any addition or deduction that wasn't in the place should be trigger"
 - Only requires a User Announcement
 - "for users not registered, they may not get the announcement"

Webex Chat Comments

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Q&A

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